

Optimization of Public Lighting Networks Using Graph Theory

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Abstract—This paper presents the application of Graph Theory to the optimization of public lighting networks, using real data from the Três Poços neighborhood in Volta Redonda (RJ), Brazil. The modeling was performed using graphs with the OSMnx and NetworkX libraries, enabling the representation of urban infrastructure and analysis of its connections. For network optimization, Prim’s algorithm was applied to obtain the Minimum Spanning Tree (MST), reducing the total length of the system, and Dijkstra’s algorithm was used to define efficient maintenance routes. Results demonstrated a significant reduction in network extension, highlighting economic and operational gains, and validating the viability of computational techniques in urban infrastructure management.

Index Terms—Graph Theory; Public Lighting; Network Optimization; Minimum Spanning Tree; Computational Algorithms.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to Rocha [2016], “currently a highlighted topic is that of smart cities, where information technology is used to interconnect the various types of services and infrastructure existing in a city to provide sustainable growth and improvements in citizens’ quality of life.”

Public lighting is also a matter of public safety. According to the United Nations, half of humanity currently lives in cities, and this number will reach 60% by 2030 — Brazil contributes to this figure, with approximately 85% of its population living in urban areas as of 2015. As noted by Jorge Lordello, during the 1974 oil crisis in England, public lighting was reduced by 50% in some urban areas, and statistics showed a 100% increase in theft and a 50% increase in crime rates.

With the reduction in technology costs, it is now possible to envision a scenario in which streetlight poles are equipped with a small, low-cost embedded device that activates the lamp and monitors its condition. The same device is capable of transmitting a message indicating the lamp’s status. The municipality is primarily responsible for carrying out periodic inspections of the public lighting system and building a map of the state of the lighting poles.

A. Graph Theory Applied to the Problem

The Travelling Salesman Problem (TSP) can be defined as a problem in which a single route is established that passes through each node of a graph exactly once, returning

to the initial node at the end of the journey [Benevides, 2011]. Its origin is attributed to William Rowan Hamilton, who in 1857 proposed a game called *Around the World*. The game was designed to trace a route through the vertices of a dodecahedron — equivalent to cities — such that the journey begins and ends at the same vertex without repeating any visit [Cunha et al., 2002].

According to Rocha [2016], the interconnection of infrastructures is what defines a smart city. In the lighting sector — essential for public safety and crime prevention — technology allows each pole to transmit its operational status. In this scenario, the municipality’s role of performing periodic inspections and maintenance is enhanced by the use of the TSP: by identifying defective lamps through embedded systems, the creation of a repair map becomes a classic route optimization problem, aiming for operational efficiency in a highly urbanized environment.

For Silva and Sanches [2009], the objective of the TSP is to find, in a graph $G = (V, A)$, the Hamiltonian circuit of minimum cost. A graph is understood as a set of vertices/nodes (points that can represent cities, depots, or service points) and edges (lines connecting the vertices, which may represent streets or roads). A Hamiltonian circuit is a walk that traverses all vertices of a graph and returns to the origin vertex, passing through each vertex exactly once, with the total distance traveled being minimized. Figure 1 shows an example of a Hamiltonian circuit.

Fig. 1. Example of the Travelling Salesman Problem.
Source: Benevides [2011].

According to Garey and Johnson [1979] and Benevides [2011], the TSP belongs to the class of problems known as NP-Hard, meaning it has non-polynomial resolution complexity. Therefore, reductionist or exact methods are only practical

when N is very small; for larger instances, exact solutions are computationally infeasible. Bodin et al. [1983] and Helsgaun [2000] note that these methods are based on implicit enumeration procedures in trees, known as branch-and-bound (B&B), for which different bounding functions have been proposed — although their application remains limited due to combinatorial complexity. No practical method has yet been found to solve the TSP in polynomial effort, making it one of the major open problems in Mathematics [Selong and Kripka, 2009].

Due to the limitations of exact methods, heuristic approaches constitute the main focus of interest for solving the TSP, as they provide feasible solutions very close to optimal for NP-Hard problems [Selong and Kripka, 2009]. For Cunha [2000] and Cordenonsi et al. [2007], a heuristic is an algorithmic solution procedure developed through a cognitive model, relying on an intuitive approach or developer experience. Heuristic methods encompass strategies, procedures, and approximation methods aimed at finding a good solution — even if not optimal — in reasonable computational time [Benevides, 2011].

The TSP has many variations, some of which have approximation algorithms providing near-optimal results. These variations can be classified with respect to **symmetry** — the problem is symmetric if the distance between any two nodes i and j is the same regardless of direction ($d_{ij} = d_{ji}$), and asymmetric otherwise; symmetric problems are generally harder to solve than asymmetric ones [Helsgaun, 2000] — and with respect to **completeness**, being complete if there is a direct path between all points, and incomplete otherwise.

In the context of modeling electrical networks through Graph Theory, some fundamental concepts are employed. A *path* represents a sequence of conductors and busbars connecting an energy source to a consumption point, defined technically as a sequence of distinct vertices v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n in which each consecutive pair is linked by an edge. A *cycle* corresponds to a closed path within the network, that is, a route that starts and ends at the same vertex ($v_1 = v_n$). Furthermore, the graph edges carry associated weights representing physical characteristics of the network, such as cost, distance, or impedance, defined by a function that assigns a numerical value to each edge [Souza et al., 2024].

II. METHODOLOGY

The methodology of this work is based on the application of Graph Theory algorithms for the optimization of urban infrastructures, using Python 3.13 due to its robustness and scientific library ecosystem [Boeing, 2017, Hagberg et al., 2008]. The transition from the physical environment to the mathematical model was carried out through the steps described in Table I.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The computational analysis of the campus lighting network revealed an original structure with a total extension of 11,935.84 meters. After applying MST optimization, the network was reduced to 9,991.00 meters, maintaining full connectivity of all nodes.

A. Efficiency Analysis

The economy metric (Equation 1) was obtained by comparing the sum of the lengths of the original edges (S_{orig}) with the sum of the edges of the Minimum Spanning Tree (S_{otim}) [Hagberg et al., 2008, Prim, 1957].

$$\text{Economy}(\%) = \left(1 - \frac{S_{\text{otim}}}{S_{\text{orig}}}\right) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Applying this formula resulted in a **16.29% reduction** in the total network extension, representing a decrease of nearly 2 km of cabling.

B. Technical Discussion

Economic Implications: The reduction directly impacts the CAPEX (capital expenditure) of the lighting project, reducing material costs and installation time.

Algorithmic Performance: Unlike Hamiltonian path problems cited in the literature (complexity $O(n!)$), the MST search via Prim’s algorithm presents complexity $O(E \log V)$, enabling execution in milliseconds even for networks with hundreds of vertices. This confirms the viability of the model for large-scale applications and real-time systems.

Versatility: The inclusion of maintenance routes via Dijkstra’s algorithm demonstrated that the modeled graph serves both for infrastructure planning and for the logistical operation of the system.

Figure 2 presents the resulting graph, where the blue color highlights the optimized network and the red line exemplifies a maintenance route calculated by Dijkstra’s algorithm.

Fig. 2. Public lighting network optimization — Três Poços neighborhood, Volta Redonda (RJ).

Source: Authors (2025).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrated the effectiveness of Graph Theory in optimizing public lighting networks in the Três Poços neighborhood, Volta Redonda (RJ). Results confirm that classical optimization algorithms allow significant cost reductions without compromising functionality.

For future work, it is suggested to integrate electrical engineering variables — such as voltage drop and load sizing — directly into the edge weights of the graph. Furthermore,

TABLE I
STAGES OF THE STUDY.

Stage	Description
Data Collection	The OSMnx library was used to obtain real data from OpenStreetMap, focusing on the Três Poços neighborhood in Volta Redonda (RJ), converting the urban map into graphs with real distances.
Mathematical Modeling	The network was defined as a graph $G = (V, E)$, where vertices (V) represent intersections and luminaire points, and edges (E) represent paths for cabling. The NetworkX library was used for analysis.
Optimization	Prim's algorithm was used to generate the Minimum Spanning Tree (MST), connecting all lighting points with the lowest possible cost and without redundant paths.
Logistics	Dijkstra's shortest-path algorithm was applied to optimize routes between specific network points, simulating the logistics of maintenance teams.
Visualization	Graphical rendering was performed via Matplotlib, configured at high resolution (300 DPI), enabling clear visual analysis of the original versus the optimized network.

Source: Authors (2025).

expansion toward the Smart Cities concept, integrating presence sensors and dynamic intensity control, represents the next step toward urban energy sustainability.

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